

"UZBEKISTAN RAILWAYS" JSC TASHKENT-SYRDARYA ANALYSIS OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF WATER-CONDUCTING PIPES LOCATED ON THE RAILWAY NETWORK

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Annotation. The article outlines the construction and technological parameters of the water-conducting pipes, which are being disposed of in the high-speed and high-speed sections of the "Uzbekistan Railways", located in the body of the railway land pelotons, the mode of their work is determined; their condition is assessed to ensure the safe movement of trains.

Keywords: artificial structures; water-conducting pipes; technical condition; operational reliability.

Аннотация. Мақолада “Ўзбекистон темир йўллари”нинг тезюар ва юқори тезликдаги участкаларида тасарруф этилаётган, темир йўл ер полотноси танасида жойлашган сув ўтказувчи қувурларнинг қурилиш-технологик параметрларини тахлили келтирилган, уларнинг ишлар режими аниқланган, поездларнинг хавфсиз ҳаракатини таъминлаш учун уларнинг ҳолати баҳоланган.

Калит сўзлар: сунъий иншоотлар; сув ўтказувчи қувурлар; техник ҳолат; эксплуатацион ишонччилик.

Introduction. Improving the Transport system and increasing the efficiency of its activities is a necessary factor in the development of the country's economy. Among the urgent tasks that should be solved in the near future in rail transport, it is possible to expand road networks, further improve the process of freight and passenger transport in rail transport, update the locomotive and wagon park with

modern traffic composition, increase the speed of movement of all categories of trains and the load weights fired in freight trains, introduce advanced innovation and

At the same time, ensuring safe and uninterrupted movement of trains is a constant and main task on the agenda. In ensuring the safe movement of freight and passengers on the railway, it is important to keep all the permanent structures and structures of the railway infrastructure always in working order, including the priority of the railway land line in various operating conditions, as well as ensuring the smoothness of the railway is one of the scientific and practical issues.

The physical and mechanical properties of the muxim indicator - grunts, which characterize the primacy and completeness of railway land Polo, depend on the humidity of the grunts in the body of the land Polo. At the same time, ensuring that the waters do not accumulate due to various destructive processes near the railway land Polo depends on the construction and technological parameters of the engineering solutions adopted in the design process, that is, selected and placed artificial water-conducting structures, the study of their operational reliability is one of the pressing issues in ensuring the safe movement of trains.

Major researchers of the world on the construction and technological parameters of water-conducting pipes and on the origin of the physical and mechanical indicators of land polotnos, malfunctions that occur in pipes during operation: the reasons for the origin of deformations that are characteristic of water-conducting pipes are explained by Steffens D. M., Selig E. T., Allemang R., Brown D., Deman A.P.; the process of construction and operation of water-conducting pipes Karputshenko N.I., Bokarev S.A., Kamenchukov A.V., Borovik G.M. , Yaroshenko V.A., Andreev O.V., Prokopovich A.G., Timashev S.A., Mirakhmedov M.M., Abdujabarov A.H., Djabbarov S.T., Raupov Ch.S., Lesov K.S. and studied in scientific and applied research by others. At the same time, the state of operation of water-conducting pipes in railways in various operational conditions, including operation under a short-acting load from the structure of movement, the reasons for

the origin of deformations and emerging malfunctions in water-conducting pipes, including the impact of the water-carrying capacity of water-conducting pipes located in the railway ground. The most common damage and deformations of stone, concrete and reinforced concrete water pipes being exploited on Railways, i.e. the development of cracks, sinks, washes and other breakdowns, the opening of deformation joints, the deposition of joints and heads and soil erosion in the pipe zone caused by waterproofing breakdowns, can be observed in large numbers (Figure 1)[1].

Figure 1. Scheme of damage and deformations of the water pipe:

1-cracks; 2 – broken fragments and partial fracture of the skin; 3 – friction; 4 –stretching of sections and deposition of the grout by forming a gap in the lifting body; 5 – deposition of Section; 6 – opening of the deformation seam; 7 –elongation of the head from the pipe body; μ - deviation of the section.

The main purpose of assessing the technical condition of artificial structures on the railway is to determine their operational suitability, determine the type of repair required and the volume of repair and restoration work for the current period. The assessment of the technical condition and composition of artificial structures being operated on the Railways of JSC " Railways of Uzbekistan " is carried out in accordance with the current instructions [2,3,4,5,6,7]. We will consider the procedure for solving the technical condition of Su'niy structures on high-speed and high-speed roads of the Tashkent 2-rail distance based on the instructions given above. There are a total of 378 Su'niy structures on the Tashkent-Samarkand section of the Tashkent 2nd railway distance, of which 61 are water-carrying pipes. These

pipes were built in 1915-2020, with the distribution of construction deadlines in years ' cross section given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Types of water-conducting pipes by installation time

№	Time of construction, years	Number	Share, %
1	1915-1930	2	3
2	1931-1945	5	8
3	1946-1960	29	48
4	1961-1975	10	16
5	1976-1990	14	23
6	2005-2020	1	2
Total		61	100%

The data presented in the table shows that more than 50% of the pipes being disposed of today are designed and built on the basis of the design criteria of 1915-1960, with an average age of 50. Various building materials such as stone, brick, concrete, reinforced concrete were used in the construction of these pipes (Table 2). Most of the pipes built in the first half of the last century were built of stone, brick, concrete.

Table 2

Types of water-conducting pipes by material

№	Types of pipes by material	Number	Share, %
1	Concrete	3	5%
2	Concrete brick	3	5%
3	Reinforced concrete	46	75%
4	Reinforced concrete brick	6	10%

5	Stone brick	3	5%
Total		61	100%

It is necessary to refine the water-conducting pipes not only in materials, but also in accordance with The Shape of the slits. The distribution of pipes currently being disposed of according to The Shape of the slit is given in Table 3.

Table 3.

Types of water-conducting pipes by slits

№	Types of pipes by cross-section	Number	Share, %
1	Round	25	41%
2	Straight net	20	33%
3	Round, straight net	16	26%
Total		61	100%

It was studied in what mode the pipes work in the process of water transfer- the current state of the pipe slit for mating (detection), that is, the degree of its contamination (filling with clots or blisters), the shrinkage of the cross-sectional surface. As a result, it was established that the pipes at the disposal are operated in a pressurized, semi-pressurized and pressurized Mode (Table 4).

Table 4

Distribution of water-conducting pipes by mode of operation

№	Distribution of pipes by mode of operation	Number	Share, %
1	Without pressure	36	59
2	Semi-pressurized	2	3

3	Pressurized	23	38
Total		61	100%

It is assumed and designed that the water-conducting pipes work in a state without pressure. The degree of turbidity of the flow of water flowing through the pipe varies, and there is a state of accumulation of heavy fractional sediments at the bottom of the pipe. This state in turn has a negative effect on the water permeability of the pipe. The degree of turbidity of the pipes being exploited is shown in Table 5[8].

Table 5

Types of conducting pipes by degree of turbidity

№	Types of pipes by degree of turbidity, %	Number	Share, %
1	15	10	16
2	20	10	16
3	30	18	30
4	40	9	15
5	60	8	13
6	80	6	10
Total		61	100%

The physical and mechanical properties of grunts on the ground polotnos body adjacent to the pipe (plasticity of the grunts, foaming, adhesion of the grunts, clotting, washing, solubility) can be observed in the time maboyne, as a result of the operation of the pipe in a pressurized mode, and as a result of a decrease in the tensile capacity of the grunt, violation of the ground polotnos (Figure 2) and loss of.

Figure 2. In the railway network, the water conductor culvert malfunctions.

Conclusion. High-speed and high-speed sections of the "Uzbekistan Railways" plan the construction and technological parameters of the water-conducting pipes located in the body of the railway land pelotons, a result of the study of their mode of work, the determination of their condition to ensure the safe movement of trains, we can summarize:

- in ensuring safe and continuous movement of trains of all categories, the technical condition of the water-conducting pipes is achieved by now;
- changes in the technical condition of the pipes, the transition from a pressurized mode to a pressurized or semi-pressurized mode of operation can lead to changes in the physical and mechanical properties of the ground floor and loss of the lifting capacity of the ground floor;
- in order to eliminate the transition of pipes from a pressurized mode to work in a pressurized or semi-pressurized mode, it is necessary to regularly monitor them and carry out cleaning at the necessary points.

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